

Workshop: Development of Competency-Based Curriculum

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Abstract

The development of a curriculum for an engineering program is always challenging as it needs to identify and address competencies that are indeed relevant for the future engineers. While engineering programs typically emphasize technical skills, competencies such as communication and teamwork are currently considered equally vital. It is important to ensure that all planned competencies are properly spread out over the student's years of education and given enough attention across different classes. The primary goal of this workshop is to tackle the challenge of balancing competencies across the various courses within an engineering program, ensuring that each course adequately covers its designated competencies. Additionally, we will explore how competencies can be effectively broken down to understand and evaluate skills, knowledge, and attitudes. We'll briefly discuss teaching methods and explore potential learning strategies with workshop participants. Furthermore, we'll address the process of writing learning objectives or outcomes for a course syllabus and close the loop by verifying whether the set of courses is indeed adhering to the program's proposal to proportionally empower students with a defined set of competencies.

Keywords: Curriculum Development; Competency Balancing; Learning Objectives.

1 Introduction

Engineering has been facing increasingly significant challenges in recent decades, such as sustainability and the fourth industrial revolution, which demand a new profile from Engineering programs' graduates (Hadgraft & Kolmos, 2020). Addressing these new challenges goes far beyond the traditional image of engineers' technical tasks and responsibilities, requiring a type of engineer capable of understanding the economic, social, and environmental contexts in which problems are embedded, and who can work both within and outside the boundaries of their own discipline (Van den Beemt et al., 2020).

Given this scenario, it becomes essential to reflect on strategies for developing Engineering curricula that foster competences beyond the technical in students, in order to prepare them to address contemporary complex problems. This reflection is even more timely considering that, for a long time, the course creation process in Engineering programs was based on the content to be taught, rather than on the skills to be developed (Orfali & Vieira, 2023).

Despite the growing interest in the integration of general competencies, also referred to as soft skills, into Engineering curricula, there is still no consensus on the best approaches to teach and assess them. However, certain insights are recurrent across many studies on the subject. According to Caeiro-Rodríguez et al. (2021),

It is generally accepted that soft skills cannot be learned passively, as raw knowledge acquisition. Students need to adopt an active role where they can experience their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses in relation to soft skills (p. 29223).

Considering the challenge of integrating general competencies into Engineering curricula and the role of active learning in this process, the primary objective of this session is to equip participants with educational tools for developing an engineering curriculum grounded in active learning strategies.

Next section outlines how this objective is intended to be achieved.

2 Activities

The session aims to offer participants strategies based on frameworks that organize competencies within an engineering program, thereby assisting in tackling the challenge of balancing competencies across various courses throughout the program's duration. The overarching goal of this process is to ensure that each course comprehensively covers its designated competencies. Additionally, the tools presented can be employed to dissect competencies to evaluate skills, knowledge, and attitudes across the engineering program.

We will also explore the process of formulating learning goals or outcomes for a course syllabus. Furthermore, we will ensure alignment by assessing whether the array of courses aligns with the program's proposal, thereby empowering students proportionally with a defined set of competencies.

The planned activity involves developing a fictitious engineering program. We will guide participants through each step using the proposed frameworks and facilitate discussions to share concerns, ideas, and strategies.

This workshop draws upon Insper's experience (Soares, Achurra & Orfali, 2016) with curriculum development for three engineering programs in 2014. This process was supported by the Olin College of Engineering (Miller, 2019; Somerville, 2005), which also has extensive experience in engineering program development.

2.1 Competencies for an Engineering Program

During the initial segment of the workshop, participants will design a hypothetical undergraduate program. Their task will be to identify the primary competencies that students should develop to become engineers. Balancing these competencies presents a significant challenge, as program coordinators in engineering education often highly prioritize technical skills. However, contemporary demands require the inclusion of general competencies, emphasizing the need for careful planning and adequate student time allocation for the development of each competence.

2.2 Competencies for a Course

The second part of the session is more focused on exploring a specific engineering course, with an emphasis on identifying and crafting learning goals for that course. This segment may spark interesting discussions, as creating effective learning goals is both challenging and crucial. Subsequently, participants can discuss various learning activities that align with the desired competencies and learning goals. The planned activity will prompt participants to brainstorm several learning strategies, which they will then classify as classical, innovative, or somewhere in between. Moreover, these learning strategies should be clearly linked to teaching specific competencies, along with indicating the intensity with which each activity is used to teach those competencies.

2.3 Assessment for a Course

The final step in this process is to verify whether the learning goals align with the assessment, which, in turn, align with students' learning experiences. This alignment is crucial for identifying essential aspects of a course and discerning others that may be unnecessary. To facilitate this process, we will briefly cover rubrics. Rubrics are powerful tools for evaluating students, but they can be challenging to create and complex to use during the evaluation process. Various formats and approaches exist for writing rubrics, but the main goal is to ensure they are easily understood by both students and evaluators, reducing subjectivity regarding learning goals.

3 Expected Results

The expected results are for session participants to become familiar with tools that can assist in developing new engineering programs. This session is not intended to deeply explore any of the tools covered, but rather to present and briefly discuss tools that can be utilized for creating engineering programs. One advantage of

using these documentation tools is that they facilitate discussions with faculty and school administration. After, throughout the program implementation, the planned goals can be monitored and adjusted as necessary.

4 References

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